

MOISTURE AGEING CHARACTERIZATION OF GLASS FIBER REINFORCED POLYAMIDE COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Due to their excellent specific properties, composite materials with organic matrix are increasingly used in various domains such as transport, aerospace or civil engineering. During their lifetime, these materials can be subjected to various aggressive environments including moisture which acts as a plasticizer of the polymer network, affecting its mechanical behavior. Besides, the heterogeneous in-depth moisture content induces a differential hygroscopic swelling that may eventually cause damage. This study firstly assesses the effects of moisture diffusion on the reliability of polyamide based composite structures. It secondly seeks to quantify the mutual coupling between the mechanical behavior and the moisture diffusion phenomenon.

To achieve this first goal, the diffusive behavior, is characterized owing to gravimetric measurements during aging in a climatic chamber and thereafter identified through the use of the Fick's model. In order to carry out a mechanical analysis of the material, the hygroscopic expansion coefficient, linking the moisture content to the hygroscopic strain, is also needed. We have developed a specific experimental device measuring the elongation of polyamide samples with a laser displacement sensor along the aging process. Based on these experimental parameters, a transient numerical study relying on an uncoupled hygro-elastic model is finally carried out to estimate the moisture and mechanical fields.

The second part of this work aims at quantifying the coupling between the moisture diffusion and the mechanical behavior. Indeed, previous experimental studies have shown that they influence each other. Mechanical tests performed at specific times during the transient stage of the moisture diffusion process enabled to determine the evolution of the mechanical properties as a function of the water content.

1 INTRODUCTION

Passenger cars are still mainly propelled owing to fossil fuels. Nevertheless, fossil fuels supply became a critical geopolitical issue during World War II and has remained so ever since [1]. Moreover fossil fuels combustion is a critical source of greenhouse gas emission. Greenhouse gases such as carbon dioxide (CO₂) may contribute to the global warming, because they are relatively long-lived in the atmosphere [2]. Fossil fuel consumption by passenger cars is strongly related to the mass of the vehicles [3]. Besides, The EU first introduced mandatory 2015 CO₂ standards for new passenger cars in 2009. According to regulation (EC) No 443/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council, the passenger car standards are 95 g/km of CO₂, phasing in for 95 % of vehicles in 2020 with 100 % compliance in 2021. Consequently, in Europe, the auto industry is looking for cutting dramatically the weight of new vehicles. In order to reach that goal, lightweight materials such as magnesium alloys [4], aluminum alloys [5], high strength steels [6], or polymer composites can be used instead of the more traditional cast iron and conventional steels. In that context, materials selection is thereby determined by economic issues as much as by materials and components characteristics or properties.

In this field of applications, glass reinforced thermoplastics tend to concentrate on polypropylene or Nylon as the base resin. The main reason can be attributed to the fact that among the engineering thermoplastics, these materials tend to be the most inexpensive whereas they are the most easily processed. Nevertheless, both these materials are sensitive to environmental conditions (temperature and moisture) relative to vehicle requirements for structural parts [7].

During their service life, passenger cars are actually submitted to variable hygroscopic environments. Polymer matrices such as polyamides may absorb significant amounts of water when exposed to humid environments. Absorbed water induces various effects such as dimensional change that occur during both the transient stage (differential swelling), and the permanent stage of the diffusion process [8, 9], [10]. Besides, moisture absorption can adversely affect most physico-mechanical properties of polymers. One of the main effects of water on polymer matrices is, among others, plasticization [11, 12], [13, 14]. Water molecules can actually be sorbed in different ways in polymers. Water can either be dispersed in the matrix (random dispersion of free, unbound molecules in the bulk of the matrix) or be associated to specific sites of the macromolecular backbone, through hydrogen bonding or polar interactions [15]. The sorption mechanisms induce a reversible reduction of both the glass transition of the polymer [16] and its mechanical properties such as the Young's modulus [17, 18], as well as the mechanical strengths [19, 20]. The effect of moisture can be a big factor in products that may be exposed to different weather conditions due to change in seasons or geographic locations. Thus, one needs to take into account this very important factor in material pre-selection stage, plastic parts design, mechanical performance prediction and optimization.

The present work will be devoted to the experimental study of polyamides and polyamide composites intended to be used for structural parts of passenger vehicles. The experimental characterization of their hygro-mechanical behaviors during hydrothermal ageing, will be first made by a fine determination of the kinetics of diffusion of these materials, in relative humidity aging conditions. Secondly, we will study the evolution, during the moisture diffusion process, of some critical properties for the design of mechanical parts: the Young's modulus, the tensile strength limits as well as the coefficient of moisture expansion. Eventually, the identified properties will be used as input parameters in order to achieve numerical computations accounting for the variability of the diffusive behavior, owing to a probabilistic model.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 MATERIALS

This study was made on glass fiber reinforced polyamide, and the corresponding PA6 neat resin, provided by Solvay (a project partner). They have a good mechanical properties such as: good resistance to a large number of chemicals products. Polyamides and their composites are used in several application fields for mechanical parts subjected to mechanical stress and high temperatures. They can also be used in mechanical automotive construction for various parts such as: plain bearing, body coils, guide and coupling parts, nuts and slides.

2.2 SAMPLES

The samples were cut with a water jet from plates (of either 2 mm or 4 mm thickness), obtained by sheet molding compound. The resulting specimen present the following geometries: a dumbbell with rounded junction according norm (ISO 3167) for tensile tests, or a parallelepiped shape of dimensions $200 \times 20 \times 2$ or $200 \times 20 \times 4$ mm^3 for kinetic and swelling identification. Several unidirectional composites with 49 % volumetric percentage of fibers were studied: UD [90°] and UD [45°]. 35 samples were dedicated to the kinetics identification, 75 to the destructive mechanical tests and 15 to the characterization of the coefficient of moisture expansion.

These samples were referenced and undergone a polishing with sandpapers with 4 grains sizes (230, 600, 1000 and 1200 μm) and a final micro polishing by alumina powder.

Preliminary to the aging tests, the samples were conditioned under a vacuum for 24 days. The water loss was followed during this stage, until a constant mass was obtained: the conditioned samples experience as a result a homogeneous in-depth moisture content.

Finally, the specimens intended to be aged are placed in a controlled climatic chamber at 80 % relative humidity (RH) and at a temperature of 24°C.

2.3 WATER SORPTION

Five specimens of each type (neat resin and unidirectional composites) undergo a gravimetric monitoring to measure the water uptake (by using a balance with precision of 10^{-4} g). Figure (Fig. 1) shows the periodicity of the gravimetric measurements achieved during the transient stage of the aging process:

Figure 1: Time axis with a numbers of measurements per period.

The time interval between 2 measures increases, as the rate of moisture absorption decreases with time, to reach a stage when one measurement by week is sufficient. The purpose of monitoring the water uptake and obtaining the classical sorption curves is to identify the kinetic diffusion of each type of investigated materials.

2.4 MOISTURE DIFFUSION THEORY: EQUATIONS AND SOLUTION

The absorption of moisture in a hydrophilic material is primarily characterized by two quantities:

- Maximum moisture absorption capacity C^∞ . It corresponds to the water content that the material can absorb in given environmental conditions, at the saturation of the diffusion process.
- The diffusion coefficient D which represents the velocity rate at which moisture enters the material.

In order to identify both parameters, one often draws the classical sorption curve, i.e. the macroscopic water content $\bar{C}(t)$ as function of the root square time. An example of diffusion curves are presented on figure (Fig. 2-a), where the water content is calculated by the following equation

$$\bar{C}(t) = 100 \frac{m(t) - m_0}{m_0} \quad (1)$$

where $m(t)$ is the weight of a specimen at time t and m_0 is the weight at the initial time. This gravimetric monitoring allows to have access to a macroscopic diffusion of the moisture content but does not allow to obtain the spatial distribution of this quantity during the absorption process. A model is thus required to study the local behavior of the moisture diffusion. There are various laws describing the sorption of a material. We will only focus on the classical uncoupled Fick model.

Figure 2: (a) Diffusion curves of 4 specimens of neat PA6 and 4 of unidirectional composites UD [45°] as a function of the root square of time. (b) Experimental and identified data with Fick solution of each material type.

Uncoupled Fick's law [21], is certainly the most commonly implemented law when one considers the diffusion of a solvent (water) in any material (such as a material composite). This model linearly connects the vector of mass flow rate of solvent to its concentration gradient. The adjective "uncoupled", refers to the fact that the interactions between the mechanical states and the diffusion process are not considered.

The first Fick law describes the relationship between the material flow J and the mass concentration gradient c such that

$$J = -D \overset{\rightarrow}{\text{grad}} c \quad (2)$$

where D is the diffusion tensor whose components represent the rate of diffusion in each principal direction.

Fick's second law describes, meanwhile, the balance of material conservation during a time interval. The law of species conservation indicates that the opposite of the change per unit time of the amount of diffusing particles in a given volume is equal to the outgoing flow

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} = -\text{div} J \quad (3)$$

Finally, the general equation of the Fick model that governs the local water diffusion in a homogeneous material results from the combination of equations (2) and (3), i-e

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} = \text{div} \left(\vec{D} \cdot \text{grad} c \right) \quad (4)$$

Moisture diffusion occurs on the boundary Γ of a geometric area Ω , on which is usually applied the boundary conditions. Typically, this boundary condition C_{imp} is imposed as a water content, which is equal to the macroscopic measured water content at saturation in a sample submitted to the same environmental conditions.

The problem thus becomes: find field c depending on time t and space (x_1, x_2, x_3) , that is to say $c(x_1, x_2, x_3, t)$ solution of:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial c}{\partial t} = \text{div} \left(\vec{D} \cdot \text{grad} c \right) & \text{on } \Omega \\ c = c_{imp} & \text{on } \Gamma \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

In an arbitrary case, problem (5) can be solved by approximation methods. However, the Crank book [21] provides analytical solutions corresponding to different simple situations depending, in particular, on the geometry of the samples, the imposed boundary conditions or some constraints on the diffusion coefficient. In the case of a conventional rectangular sample of length L , width b and thickness e , subjected to three-dimensional diffusion, the local analytical solution exists and leads, by integration on the volume, to the global moisture content

$$C(t) = \frac{m(t) - m_0}{m_s - m_0} = \left(1 - \left(\frac{8}{\pi^2} \right)^3 \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{((2i+1)(2j+1)(2k+1))^2} \right) \times \exp \left(-\pi^2 t \left(D_1 \left(\frac{2i+1}{L} \right)^2 + D_2 \left(\frac{2j+1}{b} \right)^2 + D_3 \left(\frac{2k+1}{e} \right)^2 \right) \right) \quad (6)$$

where m_0 and m_s are respectively the mass of initial water and the mass corresponding to the saturation state. A comparison between the analytical solution (6) and the experimental results of gravimetric

monitoring allows the identification of kinetic diffusion parameters (D_1, D_2, D_3 the coefficients of diffusion and C^∞ the maximum capacity of moisture absorption).

The purpose is now to determine the optimal parameters minimizing the least-squared difference q between the experimental data $\bar{C}(t)$ and the exact solution of equation (6) defined by

$$q(D_1, D_2, D_3, m_s) = \sum_{n=0}^{n_T} (C(t_n) - \bar{C}(t_n))^2 \quad (7)$$

where $\{t_n\}_{n=0}^{n_T}$ is the set of time measurements related to the set of experimental measure $\{\bar{C}(t_n)\}_{n=0}^{n_T}$. The optimization problem is solved using a classical algorithm of optimization [22] based on some assumptions on the material properties and the geometrical definition.

An example of a diffusion identification of neat resin samples and some UD [45°] is presented in the figure (Fig. 2-b). The good agreement between the identified Fick model and the experimental data shows that the studied materials absorb moisture according to a Fickian kinetics. The identified parameters are presented in table (Table 1).

Type	PA6 neat resin (200x20x2)		UD [45°] (200x20x2)		UD [90°] (200x20x2)	
	$D_3(mm^2/s)$	C^∞	$D_3(mm^2/s)$	C^∞	$D_3(mm^2/s)$	C^∞
Specimen 1	1.13E-07	3.79%	1.45E-07	1.38%	1.45E-07	1.37%
Specimen 2	1.08E-07	3.79%	1.40E-07	1.41%	1.38E-07	1.37%
Specimen 3	1.25E-07	3.83%	1.42E-07	1.43%	1.72E-07	1.41%
Specimen 4	1.28E-07	3.84%	1.39E-07	1.39%	1.42E-07	1.31%
Average	1.19E-07	3.81%	1.42E-07	1.40%	1.49E-07	1.37%
Standard deviation	9.68E-09	0.03%	2.57E-09	0.02%	1.57E-08	0.04%

Table 1: Identified Fick parameters for neat resin, UD [45°] and UD [90°] composite specimens.

The Identified Fick model parameters given in table 1 will be used in the examples described in Section 3.

2.5 MECHANICAL TESTS (CHARACTERIZATION OF THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES EVOLUTION DURING MOISTURE AGING)

75 specimens were reserved for uniaxial traction tests. It was intended to duplicate test on sets of 5 samples under reproducibility conditions. In doing so, we can get information on the dispersion of the mechanical properties.

Before water ageing in the climatic chamber and after conditioning under vacuum, 5 specimens of each type were tested immediately at time $t = 0$ to find the mechanical properties in the initial “dry” state. The periodicity of the test is 500 hours. Before each mechanical destructive test, a measurement of the dimensions of the samples was performed. The width and the length are characterized by sliding caliper (accuracy 0.02 mm) whereas the thickness was measured by a micrometer of 0.01 mm precision. The dimensional data are necessary to eventually calculate the material properties from the force-displacement curve obtained in practice.

Tensile test was performed to find the evolution, during the aging process of both the tensile modulus and the ultimate stress. For the first quantity a strain gauge was used to determine the true strain experienced by the sample. Thereafter, the strain gauge is removed and the force applied to the sample increased until failure occurs in order to find the ultimate stress. The tensile modulus was determined from the slope of the linear portion of the stress-strain curves. The ultimate tensile stress is calculated from the maximum force applied to the section of the samples.

Figure 3: (a) Evolution of the average tensile modulus as a function of the aging time (hours), (b) Evolution of the ultimate tensile stress as a function of the aging time (hours).

Tensile modulus undergoes a sharp drop at the beginning of the moisture aging, before stabilizing after 40 days (Fig. 3-a). The decrease in the modulus is the strongest for the UD [45°] samples, but it is of the same order of magnitude than results obtained on the neat resin. These results can be attributed to the plasticization of the resin: the absorbed water breaks secondary bonds between the polymer chains, by bounding themselves to the hydrophilic functional groups of the polyamide. This induces a decrease of the elasticity modulus of the resin (and therefore, to a lesser extent, of the composite). When all the hydrophilic sites are occupied, the water continues to penetrate the material, forming (clusters) between the polymer chains. This second stage of the sorption, which occurs without further physico-chemical alteration of the polymer chains, does not lead to a significant drop in the elastic stiffness. The ultimate stress of the UD [45°] and UD [90°], shown on figure (Fig. 3-b) are lower than the one of neat resin: this is mainly coming from their multilayer structure, which is severe for this type of loading.

2.6 SWELLING IDENTIFICATION

The moisture diffusion process contributes to the expansion of the polymer network. As a result, the main property related to the swelling is the coefficient of moisture expansion (β) of the neat PA6 samples. In order to determine this quantity we beforehand need to define the behavior law satisfied by, the total strain ϵ experienced by the sample: the classical hygro-elastic Hooke's law writes

$$\sigma = \mathbf{C} : (\epsilon - \beta \Delta c) \quad (8)$$

where σ stands for the stress tensor, whereas ϵ is the strain tensor, \mathbf{C} is the elastic stiffness tensor, β the tensor of the coefficients of hygroscopic expansion, and c the moisture content.

At the saturation, the moisture content is homogeneous in the neat resin, thus the stress tensor is null. As a result, ϵ is equal to βc according to (equation 8) and we can estimate the coefficient β from the measure of the dimensional change of the specimen. To estimate this quantity we need to achieve the saturation of material by water. In order to reach this goal, a specific experimental device has been developed: it measures the elongation of the polyamide samples with a laser displacement sensor during the aging process. The measuring apparatus is shown in the figure (Fig. 4-a). It is constituted by a laser displacement sensor LK-081 (KEYENCE), a controller LK-2101 (KEYENCE) and a multi-meter.

The specimens are always positioned at the same locus by means of 5 punctual stands. The variation of length is calibrated by an etalon at room temperature and humidity, the etalon has a dimensions which are considered constant and unaffected by the external environment effects.

Figure 4: (a) Operating apparatus designed for elongation determination, (b) Elongation ($\frac{\Delta L}{L_0}$) according to the global water content \bar{c} of the neat PA6 resin samples

The variation ΔU represents the difference between the voltage indicated by the voltmeter for the sample and that given for the standard. The variation of the sample length (ΔL) is then determined by taking into account the sensitivity of the measurement chain. We can thus find the longitudinal strain ($\epsilon_x \approx \frac{\Delta L}{L_0}$).

The magnitude of the uncertainty on the variation of the sample length, calculated on the whole measurement process is 7 μm , taking into account the uncertainty that comes from the laser sensor, controller, multimeter as well as the repeatability. Figure (Fig. 4-b) shows a plot of the elongation versus macroscopic water content, obtained on a set of samples of neat PA6 resin.

The method of identification required to determine the swelling coefficient is described in Section 3 of this article.

3 MODELLING OF HYGRO-MECHANICAL PROBLEM AND NUMERICAL STUDIES

In this section, we propose two numerical studies. Firstly, a deterministic study aims at showing the importance of taking into account a dependence of the hygroscopic expansion coefficient to the local water content. Secondly, we propose a probabilistic study where the uncertainties relating to the diffusive properties are considered.

3.1 DIFFUSION PROBLEM

We consider a spatial domain Ω , and we denote by \mathbf{x} the position vector of a material point at a given time t . We assume a Fickian diffusion model for which the local problem can be written: find the local moisture field $c(\mathbf{x}, t) \in \Omega \times R_*^+$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial c(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t} &= \mathbf{D} \Delta c(\mathbf{x}, t) && \text{on the } \Omega \times R_*^+ \\ c(\mathbf{x}, t) &= c_{imp} && \text{on the } \Gamma_c \times R_*^+ \\ c(\mathbf{x}, 0) &= c_0(\mathbf{x}) && \forall \mathbf{x} \in \Omega \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where Γ_c is a part of the boundary $\Gamma = \partial \Omega$ of the domain Ω , c_{imp} is the imposed content and \mathbf{D} the diffusion tensor. Besides for a few simple cases, there is no analytical solution to the problem (equation 9) and approximation methods are thus needed. We use the conventional finite element method using the Abaqus© software. The solution of the problem at a time t is then contained in the vector $\mathbf{c}(t)$ whose components correspond to the nodes of the finite element mesh.

3.2 HYGRO-ELASTIC PROBLEM

We seek to obtain the displacement field $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x})$ induced by swelling of the material involved by the moisture field at a given time t . We consider a linear elastic material and we work under small perturbations assumption. The local problem can be written: find the field $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) \in \Omega$ such that

$$\begin{aligned}
\operatorname{div} \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \mathbf{f} &= 0 && \text{on } \Omega \\
\boldsymbol{\sigma} &= \mathbb{C} : (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \boldsymbol{\beta} c) && \text{on } \Omega \\
\mathbf{u} &= \mathbf{u}_{imp} && \text{on } \Gamma_u
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

where \mathbf{u}_{imp} is the imposed displacement on Γ_u a part of the boundary. This problem is solved by the finite element method to characterize the solution by a vector \mathbf{u} whose components correspond to the set of the finite element nodes.

The hygroscopic expansion coefficient β is often assumed to be constant and is determined according to a homogeneous water content field as explained in section 2.6. However, such modeling does not represent a non-linear evolution of the elongation as seen in figure (Fig. 4-b). We thus propose to take into account local variations of β with respect to the local water content c through the following sigmoid function

$$\beta(c) = \frac{\beta_{max}}{1 + \exp(-\lambda A(c))} \tag{11}$$

where β_{max} is the value of the expansion coefficient obtained with the homogeneous moisture field corresponding to a saturated state, λ is a parameter controlling the shape of the sigmoid and the coefficient $A(c)$ is given by

$$A(c) = \left(\frac{2c - c_s}{2c_s} \right) \tag{12}$$

where the water content c_s is a threshold value, from which $\beta(c) = \beta_{max}$, which may be different from c_{imp} . The experimental determination of the parameters λ and c_s is not easy. However, starting from the evolution of the relative elongation versus the global water content (Fig. 4-b), it is possible to formulate an inverse problem, based on this information and on numerical simulations, which provides the optimal values of these two parameters λ and c_s .

3.3 NUMERICAL EXAMPLE A

We consider the problem of a plate of size 200x2 mm² (Fig. 5), whose mesh is composed of 8000 three-nodes triangles. The input parameters are given in the table (Table 2), where the diffusion parameters are those identified experimentally and the parameters λ and c_s are optimal values of the local model defined by (equation 11) and (equation 12). The computation is done with an implicit Euler scheme for a calculation period of $T = 2,5 \times 10^7$ s (9.6 months) and a time step increment $\Delta t = 172800$ s (or 2 days).

Figure 5: Geometry and mesh of hygro-mechanical problem.

hygroscopic parameters		mechanical parameters	
Isotropic diffusion coefficient	$D = 1.19e^{-7} (mm^2/s)$	Young's modulus	$E = 3800$ MPa
Boundary condition on Γ_c	$c_{imp} = 3.81 \% H_2O$	Poisson ratio	$\nu = 0.35$
		Model parameters	$\beta_{max} = 0.295$ $\lambda = 6$ and $c_s = 2.6 \%$

Table 2: Input parameters of the hygro-mechanical problem.

The sigmoidal model (equation 11) and (equation 12) leads to a coefficient β which depends on the local moisture content. This dependence is illustrated in the figure (Fig. 6-a). With this model, it is possible to simulate the nonlinear behavior changes $\frac{\Delta L}{L_0}$ as shown in figure (Fig. 6-b) where the numerical results well fit the experimental data.

Figure 6: (a) Local model of the hygroscopic expansion coefficient in function of the water content (local), (b) Comparison between numerical results and experimental data.

The local behavior law for the coefficient of moisture expansion of the PA6 neat resin was identified by comparing the results of numerical simulations with the experimental data. This local behavior law presents several outstanding features. Firstly, the local moisture expansion coefficient of polyamide 6 tends towards 0 when the material is dry (conditioning state). This property is consistent with the predictions obtained owing to molecular dynamics [23]. From a chemical mechanistic point of view, locally, the first water molecules absorbed by an area of the initially dry material are attached by the most hydrophilic sites of the polymer network. Water molecules experience strong interactions in the vicinity of hydrophilic groups, and can form hydrogen bond(s). Type I water molecules form a single hydrogen bond with the polymer network, whereas type II water molecules form 2 hydrogen bonds, possibly connecting together 2 polymer chains. Overall, these changes in the physico-chemical structure of the polymer network yields a plasticization effects that can reduce the stiffness of the material. Nevertheless plasticization occurs without significantly changing the distance between the neighboring polymer chains: the resulting hygroscopic swelling is reduced. However, when all of the hydrophilic sites are already occupied by water molecules, the water molecules that are sorbed thereafter start to form clusters of so-called "free water" between the polymer chains. The size of these clusters grows, pushing the polymer chains: the volume change associated with the penetration of a given amount of water increases in proportion to the size of the clusters until the maximum size of these clusters is reached. This explains the quasi-linear increase as a function of the water content of the local coefficient of moisture identified in the figure (Fig. 6-a), until a final value which no more depends on the water content is attained. Such non-linearities of hygroscopic expansion have already been reported in the literature, in the specific case of nylon 6 thread [24].

3.4 PROBABILISTIC MODELING

We are now interested in taking into account the uncertainties on the diffusive properties of the material shown in the figure (Fig. 2-a). To achieve this task, we adopt a parametric vision of the uncertainties resulting in working in a probability finite dimension space. The probabilistic content is then represented by a set of independent random variables represented by the vector ξ . These random variables are used to characterize the various random input, such as material properties or loading. The problem defined by (equation 13) and (equation 14) thus depends on random parameters as well as their discretized solutions $c(t, \xi)$ and $u(\xi)$. In order to quantify the uncertainties on these responses, it is necessary to use dedicated computational techniques. The most famous of them is the Monte Carlo method which consists in generating a large number of input random realizations and to evaluate the

system response for each of them. This method is easy to implement and especially provides a good estimate of the statistical moments. However, it may require a large number of deterministic calculations and leads to significant computational time. We then choose to use a different calculation technique, leading to a functional representation of the random response, which requires a few deterministic calculations when the number of random input variables is low.

3.5 STOCHASTIC APPROXIMATION BY POLYNOMIAL CHAOS

An alternative approach to the Monte Carlo method is to seek a solution $c(\mathbf{x}, t, \xi)$ in the form of the following approximation

$$c(\mathbf{x}, t, \xi) \approx \sum_{\alpha=1}^P c_{\alpha}(\mathbf{x}, t) H_{\alpha}(\xi) \quad (13)$$

where the $\{H_{\alpha}(\xi)\}_{\alpha=1}^P$ forms a basis of the space of second-order random variables and where the coefficients $c_{\alpha}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ are the unknowns of the problem. Note that the solution $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t, \xi)$ of the hygro-elastic problem is sought in the same form. There are several choices for functions H_{α} : we here use the polynomial chaos expansion consisting in taking multi-dimensional orthonormal polynomials. This is a particular construction of the base where the H_{α} functions are multi-dimensional orthonormal polynomials respecting the probability measure of the random input variables [25, 26].

There are several methods to compute the coefficients $c_{\alpha}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, and here, we use a L^2 projection technique which consists in defining the discretized solution as the projection on the stochastic approximation space of the semi-discretized solution $\mathbf{c}(t, \xi)$ [27]. This technique is a non-intrusive method which solely requires the resolution of a finite number of deterministic problems corresponding to particular realization of ξ . The fully discrete solution at a given time t will be represented by the following development

$$\mathbf{c}(t, \xi) \approx \sum_{\alpha=1}^P c_{\alpha}(t) H_{\alpha}(\xi) \quad (14)$$

Once this form obtained, it becomes simple and fast to estimate the solution for particular realization of ξ or the probability density function of the response.

3.6 NUMERICAL EXAMPLE B

In this section we resume the previous example A studying the resin and we consider the parameters D and c_{imp} as a random variables. These variables respectively follow the following normal distributions $N(1.19 * 10^{-7}, 9.68 * 10^{-9})$ and $N(3.81 \%, 0.03 \%)$ and represent the probabilistic content of the problem. However, unlike the example A, we simply assume a constant swelling coefficient $\beta = 0.295$ without local dependency. For the stochastic approximation we use a polynomial chaos of order 2 which leads to a number of polynomials $P = 6$. The computation of the response required 16 deterministic calculations corresponding to particular values of D and c_{imp} for a total calculation time of 30 minutes on a standard laptop computer. The results are shown on figures (Fig. 7-a) and (Fig. 7-b). Figure (Fig. 7-a) shows the mean and the confidence interval at 99% of the evolution of the global water content as a function of time. We can see that the probabilistic model well represent the uncertainties present in the experimental data. Figure (Fig. 7-b) shows the time evolution of the local stress σ_{11} at a point x_1 , located in the center of the plate. We observe a rapid increase at the first instants of the process and then a slow decline tending to 0 MPa corresponding to the saturated state of the resin for which the elastic stress is theoretically equal to zero. Finally, it can be seen through the provided confidence interval that the level of uncertainty is similar to one observed on the overall water content with a maximum coefficient of variation close to 6%.

Figure 7: (a) Evolution of the global content as a function of aging time (mean and confidence interval). (b) Evolution of the stress σ_{11} function of aging time (mean and confidence interval).

4 CONCLUSION

We have proposed a study of hygro-elastic behavior of composite materials made of polyamide PA6. Firstly, we have experimentally determined the physical properties that govern the choice of the model and quantified the impact of moisture diffusion on elastic properties. It clearly appeared in the case of PA6 that these properties decreased. Besides, an experimental device was presented to monitor the evolution of the hygroscopic expansion with aging. The results showed that this evolution was not linear, and a model was thus proposed to represent this behavior. A deterministic numerical study has shown the good behavior of the model regarding the experimental information. Finally, significant uncertainties have been observed on the diffusion phenomenon, mainly on the diffusion coefficient. These uncertainties have been taken into account using a probabilistic model whose resolution was made by a stochastic spectral approach with reasonable computation time. We have shown that this type of approach leads to more robust predictions and reproduced the full range of experimental data. In the short term, the next objectives are: i) take into account the decrease of mechanical properties with aging including the elastic modulus with an approach similar to the one proposed for the swelling coefficient; ii) coupling the probabilistic approach with the new proposed local models to tackle the randomness on the local evolution of the swelling coefficient and elastic properties.

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